

ISic3419

I.Sicily inscription 3419

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

limestone

Object

block

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Soluntum

Place of origin (modern)

Solunto

Provenance

Found winter 2006/7 within the wall of the building of the 'altar with three betyls' by the agora (38.093374, 13.531964)

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Solunto, Area Archeologica e
Antiquarium di Solunto

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR136794

1. Τὸ κοιν [ὄν ---]
2. Σέξστον Πεδ ρ [υκαῖον]
3. ἀντιστρ ᾶ [τηγον]
4. τὸν αὐτῶν [πάτρωνα]
5. εὐνοίας ἔ [νεκα]

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645620

EDR 136794
EDCS 64900499

Bibliography

Calascibetta, A. M. G., Di Leonardo, L. 2012. Un nuovo documento epigrafico da Solunto. In Ampolo, C.(eds.), *Sicilia occidentale. Studi, rassegne, ricerche*. Pisa. pp. 37-47.

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